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“CHILD #21”

In a quiet park on a sunny day,
A nurse and a child walk their way.
The world says it's Down Twenty One.
The neighbor spoke, and the story began.

Beneath the wide and open sky,
No heavy words can float nearby.
The child runs free, the child laughs loud,
Pure joy spilling from a heart unbound.

I begin to smile and watch nearby,
Seeing no difference, not seeing why.
For in that laugh, so warm and mild,
I see nothing but a happy child.

The world may mark a different need,
A slower step, a gentler speed.
But I see courage, pure and bright,
A special, resilient inner fight.

In a moment, soft and mild,
The world feels simple—just and styled.
Just a healer,
And just a child... twenty-one.